

groundbreaking research...

educational affiliations...

conferences
& other publicity...

national recognition...

Science, technology, music, art...

Where students achieve the impossible...

Who we are

Open to every age, ethnicity and ability

Current age range is 8-18

What we are interested in

Robotics

Music

Art

Code Breaking

Genetics

Games software

Video production

Medicine

Journalism

Chemistry

Technology

Radio

ALMOST ANYTHING YOU WANT TO LEARN MORE ABOUT

Join our team of volunteers. Choose your own project and take it as far as you can... attend conferences, publish articles, be creative!

Real projects that make a real difference in peoples lives...

Science, technology, music, art...
Where students achieve the impossible...

Anyone can get involved

Inglewood High School students are involved with a student radio station, computer games writing, rocket design, and video production.

Discover your talents

We've proven age is no barrier when you are motivated to achieve your dreams and ambitions...

Join our team of volunteers.

Choose your own project and take it as far as you can... fast-track your education and discover that learning is fun!

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Achievements

A Year 9 student presented research and a Year 12 student was invited to speak at an international Science conference in 2001

One of our students passed School Certificate Science when she was 8 years old

We have access to fully equipped teaching and research labs at WITT

Through WITT it is possible to complete Year 12 and 13 of High School in one year – and in only 10 hours per week! Fast-track your education!

Our website has won a number of awards

What do you want to achieve?

Join our team of volunteers. Choose your own project and take it as far as you can... make movies, build equipment, explore new ideas, be creative!

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Contact us

Nexus Research Group Charitable Trust
www.nexusresearchgroup.com

Michael Fenton
Head of Physics
Inglewood High
School

Marie Barrett
Principal
St John Bosco
Primary

Christine Fenton
Course coordinator
WITT

The Trusts goals include:

Creating an environment that is learner-centred, continuous and coordinated which encourages creative and complex thinking, and which gives individuals the desire to search for greater understanding.

Join our team of volunteers. Choose your own project and take it as far as you can... invent, create, publish!

Real projects that make a real difference in peoples lives...